

Age and Gender as moderating variables in Adolescent's Depression: Implications for Counselling and Psychopathology

Uwakwe, Rowland Chukwuemeka¹ & Awoke, Ngozi Ngwanma PhD²

^{1&2} Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education,
Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5762726>

Abstract

This study investigated the age and gender factors of 30 randomly selected adolescents' response to depression pattern. It was hypothesized that adolescents on the basis of age and gender will differ in their early and late period of depressive conditions. The participants' age range was between 11 and 22 years while their mean age was 15.63 years. Sub-section "D" of the Adolescent Personal Data Inventory (APDI) was the research measure adopted. The t-test statistic at 0.05 alpha level was used. The findings showed that late adolescents are more depressed than those in their early adolescence. They showed high mean score comparison in their degree of psychopathology. Further finding indicate that the female adolescents are more depressed than their male counterparts. The female adolescents showed higher mean score of 115.24 as against the male participants with 104.88 mean score. The higher the mean scores, the more of the psychopathologies manifested.

Keywords: Age, Gender, Moderating Variables, Adolescent's Depression, Psychopathology and Counselling.

Introduction

Depression in adolescents is a serious public health concern. Adolescence is an important period in developing knowledge and skills, learning how to manage emotions and relationships and acquiring attributes and abilities for adulthood. Depression in adolescence is a common mental health issue with a prevalence of 4–5% especially in mid to late adolescence (Costello, Egger, and Angold. 2005). Depression has further been identified as the principal cause of illness and disability around the globe. The World Health Organization (WHO) over the years has warned about the pathology, given that it affects over 300 million people all over the world and is characterized by a high risk of suicide, the second most common

cause of death in those aged between 15 and 29, (World Health Organization and can also lead to social and educational impairments (WHO), 2017). Consequently, identifying and treating this disorder is crucial. Recent epidemiological data on adolescent depression show that approximately 11 percent of adolescents will experience depression (Avenevoli, Swendsen, He, Burstein & Merikangas, 2015), and these episodes are associated with downstream negative consequences later in adolescence (e.g., academic difficulties, risky behavior engagement, non-suicidal self-injury) and adulthood (e.g., lower income levels, higher divorce rates, suicidality) Auerbach, Tsai & Abela, 2010; Avenevoli, Knight, Kessler & Merikangas, 2008). Most notably, an alarming 75 percent of individuals experiencing depression during adolescence will make a suicide attempt in adulthood (Nock, Green, et al., 2013).

However, while the factors sustaining adolescents depression are good index for the appreciation of the disturbing trend, several models are often necessary for charting their pathology. In psychopathological studies therefore, more interest is generated when fundamental causations are known. This is because it should facilitate active psycho-therapeutic ventures that are result oriented. This will positively direct and predict eventual therapeutic expectations in client- therapist relationship

The extant literature indicates the prevalence of depression among adolescents. The empirical finding that adolescents could be affected by mood disorder refuted the belief that this age group would lack the maturity to experience depressive symptoms (Luby, 2010). By now, childhood depression is a recognized clinical disorder, thus directing researchers towards other questions. What are the most common symptoms children and adolescents express? Do symptoms differ between boys and girls? Do symptomatic differences exist as a function of age?

Thus, in adolescence, complaints of pain are less frequent - taking their place: a decrease in school performance; increased intolerance for routine; social withdrawal; hopelessness; thoughts of guilt, irritability, rebellion; general disinterest; weariness and fatigue; preoccupation with body image; indecision and violent suicides. It is also common for the adolescent to feel bored and empty rather than depressed (Luby, Gaffrey, Tillman, Abril & Belden, 2014)

Another aspect to note is the difference in the presentation of depressive symptoms in relation to gender (Hamilton, Hamlat, Stange, Abramson & Alloy, 2014). There is no consensus in the literature in this regard. According to some authors (Chrisman, Egger, Compton, Curry & Goldston, 2006; Eapen & Crncec, 2012; Harkness, Alavi, Monroe, Slavich, Gotlib & Bagby, 2013; Thapar, Collishaw, Pine & Thapar, 2012), the contrast between boys and girls appears between the ages of 12 and 14 years, when the girls begin to show a greater number of depressive symptoms than boys. Other researchers, however, observed these differences somewhat later, between 15 and 18 years old (Essau, Lewinsohn, Seeley & Sasagawa, 2010).

Luby, Gaffrey, Tillman, Abril and Belden, (2014) found that differences between the genders may be related to socialization, hormones and/or stressful events associated with adolescence. According

to Baptista (2011) and Girgus and Yang (2015), they stem from social and educational practices of power and control, physical abuse, emotional management and coping strategies, ruminating negative thoughts, sexual orientation and negative body image.

Also according to the literature, boys exhibit more externalizing symptoms, while girls possess more internalizing symptoms (Fanti & Henrich, 2010; Keegstra, Post & Goorhuis-Brouwer, 2010). The externalizing symptoms involve impulsivity, physical or verbal aggression, agitation and provocation. Internalizing may be observed as excessive worry, withdrawal, sadness, shyness, insecurity and fear (Benarous, Hassler, Falissard, Consoli & Cohen, 2015).

Sorensen, Nissen, Mors and Thomsen (2005) investigated possible differences in depressive symptoms linked to age and gender in a clinical sample of 199 children between 8-13 years of age. In relation to age, the older participants (12-13 years) showed differences in anhedonia, hypersomnia, loss of appetite and decreased ability to concentrate, while the younger participants (8-11 years) expressed more feelings of worthlessness. No significant differences were found according to gender.

Baji, Lopez-Duran, Kovacs, George, Mayer, Kapornai and Vetro, (2009) evaluated 559 children and adolescents from 7 to 15 years of age diagnosed with depression. Two psychiatrists evaluated the results and verified the existence of different symptom patterns between age and gender groups. The authors explained that depressed mood and irritability were the most common symptoms among children and anhedonia was the least frequent. Regarding age, the symptoms altered significantly by year, with depressed mood, hypersomnia, motor retardation, fatigue, thoughts of death and suicidal ideation increased in intensity according to the child's development, while motor restlessness decreased. Girls were more prone to anhedonia, hypersomnia, insomnia and somatic complaints. The study suggests that, contrary to previous reports, a depressed mood is extremely common in this population and that the presentation of depression becomes more neurovegetative both with age and for females, including symptoms that reflect the body processes, such as sleep and motor functioning.

Studies on depression in children and adolescents suggest that, prior to puberty, there is a trend for boys to have more depressive symptoms than girls (Diamantopoulou, Verhulst & van der End, 2011; Johnson & Whisman, 2013; Rohde, Lewinsohn, Klein, Seeley & Gau, 2014). Around the age of 13 to 14 years, girls begin to consistently present higher depression rates.

Petersen, Sarigiani and Kennedy (1991), in a longitudinal study of children aged 11 to 17 years found sex differences in depressed mood before the age of 13 years, which were intensified at the age of 16 and 17 years, when the girls had higher scores than boys. In fact, there is a gap in the literature about evidence that could explain the differences in the principal symptoms among children and adolescents, and whether girls and boys divide into groups of specific symptoms, which could require different correction forms of assessment tools (Carle, Millsap & Cole, 2008).

Although there is some agreement about the symptomatic differences between children and adolescents, there is no consensus about which symptoms are typical for each age group. Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess whether or not differences in depressive symptoms are a function of gender and age group.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the age difference of the adolescents in short term depression pattern and the differences in the adolescents' depression pattern based on gender. The need to understand the multi-causatory explanation underlying their depression is increasingly getting to be urgent.

Research Hypotheses

Two research hypotheses designed in two-tailed format were investigated as follows:

1. There is no significant difference between the depression pattern of adolescents in their early and late periods
2. Adolescents on the basis of gender will not significantly differ in their pattern of depression

Methods

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. This was necessary in an attempt to establish the psychopathology of adolescent's depression. The population for this study consists adolescent students in Aba Urban. Thirty participants were selected following the initial screening of 120 secondary school students within Aba urban, Abia state southeast Nigeria. The random sampling technique was the ball of paper type which initially had "odd" and "even" written with corresponding "yes" and "No" well mixed and shaken. Thirty students of equal sexes were finally selected while their age range was between 11 and 22 years, their mean age was 15.63 years.

Instrument for Data Collection

The sub-section 'D' of the Adolescent Personal Data Inventory (APDI) was the research measure adopted for this study. The APDI, developed by Akinboye (1977) comprises ten sub-sections labeled 'A-J'.

APDI is an inventory designed to measure and meet adolescents varied needs, sub section "D" strictly on the psychopathological issues. This sub section comprise of 30 items which summarily reflect different dimensions of the adolescents 'real self' which easily defines what the adolescent thinks. This sub-section is designed to predict the adolescent's disposition or degree of depression. According to the author, many of the items indicate distorted thought process and sometimes illogical feeling that may indicate that the adolescent does not face reality of situations (Akinboye, 1977, P.17).

APDI is a five point scale. In other words the maximum score in the psychopathology section "D" is 150. A score of 120 in this sub-section represents a high degree of psychopathology while a score of 60 represents a minimum need in an averagely adjusted or normal adolescents. When the score of below 40 is

obtained a low degree of abnormal behaviour and a corresponding high degree of mental health in the adolescent would be observed.

The APDI sub-section “D” following the internal method of validation indicated a co-efficient alpha of $r=0.67$ (p.17) and, using the test-retest paradigm, the reliability of $r=0.93$ was established (p.18).

Data Analysis

The t-test statistic was used in the quantification of data. The 0.05 alpha level was however utilized for effecting statistical decisions.

Results and Findings

The results following the computed statistical details are summarized in the two tables below.

Hypothesis 1

The findings of the first hypothesis showed that the result was statistically significant. The observed t-value of 3.89 as compared to the critical t-value of 2.048 failed to confirm the hypothesis. Other statistical details are as indicated in table 1 below.

Table 1: Differential performance of early and late Adolescents in depression pattern

Category of Variables	N	X	SD	t-Cal.	df	P
Adolescents	15	97.52	33.16	3.89	28	**
Late Adolescents	15	105.6	30.56			

** (significant at 0.05)

Hypothesis 2

The findings of the second hypothesis showed that the result was statistically significant. The observed t-value of 5.62 as compared to the critical t-value of 2.048 did not support the hypothesis tested. Further statistical details are provided in table 2 below.

Table 2: Differential performance of Adolescents in depression pattern on basis of gender

Category of Variables	N	X	SD	t-Cal	df	P
Male	15	104.88	41.21	5.62	28	**
Female	15	115.24	30.08			

** (significant at 0.05)

Discussion

The results from this study indicate that adolescents at different age levels of early and late periods differ in their exposure to depression stimuli. It showed that while adolescents in their early period may not be so much disturbed psychopathologically, those in the late adolescents are. The findings of this study agrees with Sorensen, Nissen, Mors and Thomsen (2005) who investigated possible differences in depressive symptoms linked to age and gender in a clinical sample of 199 children between 8-13 years of age. They found that in relation to age, the older participants (12-13 years) showed differences in anhedonia, hypersomnia, loss of appetite and decreased ability to concentrate, while the younger participants (8-11 years) expressed more feelings of worthlessness. Perhaps, one strong reason for this discrepancy is that while adolescents in their early life are not so much pre-occupied with some economic problems those in the late adolescents are. They could be thinking of emotional relationships, some could be dating and being traumatized in their relationships. However, while the paper argues this way, it is also important to emphasize, that while these factors may not independently trigger depression for the child, the combination of these could. More importantly, previous relationship experiences are strong indices for the onset, variability and the dimension of depressive condition.

The second hypothesis predicted that adolescents on the basis of gender will not significantly differ in their pattern of depression. For one, while the argument for individual uniqueness is a welcomed development, arguing otherwise could not have been any sensible. However the findings showed that the female adolescents with high mean score are more prone to depressive conditions. The findings of this study agrees with Petersen, Sarigiani and Kennedy (1991), who in a longitudinal study of children aged 11 to 17 years found sex differences in depressed mood before the age of 13 years, which were intensified at the age of 16 and 17 years, when the girls had higher scores than boys. Other researchers like (Chrisman, Egger, Compton, Curry & Goldston, 2006; Eapen & Crncec, 2012; Harkness, Alavi, Monroe, Slavich, Gotlib & Bagby, 2013; Thapar, Collishaw, Pine & Thapar, 2012), found that the contrast between boys and girls appears between the ages of 12 and 14 years, when the girls begin to show a greater number of depressive symptoms than boys.

This may be as a result that women get more mature early than men counterparts. While adolescent male child may not so much bother in going into any romantic relationship, the female adolescents who are already in their late adolescence are easily bothered. They can brood over unnecessary things. While it is not the intension of this paper to paint the adolescent females in a bad light, their needs and cravings are however different from the adolescent males. It is these needs, desires and cravings which easily define their perception of psychopathological cases

Implications for Counselling and Psychopathology

a) Counselling

Adolescent depression is a serious mental health problem that gives rise to the feeling of sadness and loneliness. It affects how the youth thinks, feels and behaves which may lead to various emotional, behavioural and functional problems. Depression symptoms likely won't get better on their own and they may get worse or lead to other problems if untreated. Depressed adolescents may be at risk of suicide, even if signs and symptoms don't appear to be severe.

Adolescent's depression demands attention as there are no sure short ways to prevent the cause of depression, but Counselling can help adolescents to overcome it. The counselor is a very trained and friendly person in front of whom the adolescent can put his heart out and share all his desires and feelings. The Counsellor is expected to offer client unbiased opinions and ways to sort out the problem.

Counseling provides a safe place and an impartial third party to talk to. Adolescents might not want to discuss serious personal issues with parents, or might fear repercussions in talking to parents about depression. Talking to a licensed counsellor helps. Additionally, sometimes a psychiatrist might be necessary in order to prescribe medication that can lessen the symptoms of depression

Counseling helps to increase the self-esteem of an individual, boosts them to deal with issues positively when those arise rather than running away from the problem or neglecting it. Counseling helps the adolescents to break their self-isolation and reach out to their friends and make new ones. This gives them a sense of social belongingness and supports them morally.

Although depression is evil, no matter what age it occurs; counselling and proper treatment can help you come out of it easily, happily and faster.

b) Psychopathology

The study of Halley (1997) underpin the causes and maintenance of depression as bio-physical and socio-psychological, the transient nature and the implication of other depressive categorizations often dictate wider and more complex scope. These are complex issues as some fatalistic components which ordinarily are also implicated are part of clinical investigations which are on-going. Our predicaments are, while we are hearing of several instances where supernatural forces and wicked beings are implicated in depressive conditions, the extent to which these are assessable for evaluation needs more research attention. Within the present research limitation therefore, the implication of the adolescents at different age status of early and late adolescents period as well as gender factors thus constitute the scope of this study

Conclusion

In general, the results corroborated the literature while others did not, evidencing that the test should adopt different standards depending on age and gender While the indices of age as well as gender are contributory

to understanding and assessing adolescents' depressive conditions. The psycho-pathology of the depression is quite enormous. The factors maintaining adolescents' depression are equally complex and to some extent are gender specific.

Adolescent depression is a serious mental health problem that gives rise to the feeling of sadness and loneliness. It affects how the adolescent thinks, feels and behaves which may lead to various emotional, behavioural and functional problems. Although depression is evil, no matter what age it occurs; counselling and proper treatment can help you come out of it easily, happily and faster.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and the discussions that followed, it was recommended as follows:

- 1) Since adolescents in their early period may not be so much disturbed psychopathologically as those in the late adolescents, early counselling and proper treatment can prevent depression and help depressed adolescents come out of it easily.
- 2) School counsellors should pay closer attention to female adolescents since they are more prone to depressive conditions.

Reference

- Akinboye, J.O. (1977). Adolescent Personal Data Inventory (APDI), University of Ibadan. Department of Guidance & Counselling.
- Akinboye, J.O. (1977). Adolescent Personal Data Inventory Handbook: A manual for Users of the APDI, University of Ibadan.
- Avenevoli, S., Swendsen, J., He, J.P., Burstein, M. & Merikangas, K.R. (2015). Major depression in the national comorbidity survey-adolescent supplement: prevalence, correlates, and treatment. *Journal of American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 54(1), 37-44.e32.
- Baji, I., Lopez-Duran, N. L., Kovacs, M., George, C. J., Mayer, L., Kapornai, K. & Vetro, A. (2009). Age and sex analyses somatic complaints and the symptom presentation of childhood depression in a Hungarian clinical sample. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 70(10), 1467-1472
- Baptista, M.N. (2011). *Escala Baptista de Depressão - Versão Infanto-Juvenil* [Baptista Depression Scale - Toddlers and Teens version] (EBADEP-IJ). Itatiba, SP: Universidade São Francisco
- Benarous, X., Hassler, C., Falissard, B., Consoli, A. & Cohen, D. (2015). Do girls with depressive symptoms exhibit more physical aggression than boys? A cross sectional study in a national adolescent sample. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Mental Health*, 9, 41.
- Carter, J.D., Joyce, P.R., Mulder, R.T., Luty, S.E. & McKenzie, J. (2000). Gender differences in the presentation of depressed outpatients: A comparison of descriptive variables. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 61(1-2), 59-67.

- Chrisman, A., Egger, H., Compton, S.N., Curry, J. & Goldston, D.B. (2006). Assessment of childhood depression. *Child and Adolescent Mental Health, 11*(2), 111-116.
- Costello, E.J, Egger, H. & Angold, A. (2005). 10-year research update review: the epidemiology of child and adolescent psychiatric disorders: I. Methods and public health burden. *Journal of American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry, 44*(10), 972–986.
- Diamantopoulou, S., Verhulst, F.C. & Van-der-Ende, J. (2011). Gender differences in the development and adult outcome of co-occurring depression and delinquency in adolescence. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology, 120*(3), 644-655.
- Eapen, V. & Crncec, R. (2012). Strategies and challenges in the management of adolescent depression. *Current Opinion in Psychiatry, 25*(1), 7-13.
- Essau, C.A., Lewinsohn, P.M., Seeley, J.R. & Sasagawa, S. (2010). Gender differences in the developmental course of depression. *Journal of Affective Disorders, 127*(1-3), 185-190.
- Fanti, K.A. & Henrich, C.C. (2010). Trajectories of pure and co-occurring internalizing and externalizing problems from age 2 to age 12: Findings from the National Institute of Child Health and Human Development Study of Early Child Care. *Developmental Psychology, 46*(5), 1159-1175.
- Girgus, J.S. & Yang, K. (2015). Gender and depression. *Current Opinion in Psychology, 4*, 53-60.
- Hamilton, J.L., Hamlat, E.J., Stange, J.P., Abramson, L.Y. & Alloy, L. B. (2014). Pubertal timing and vulnerabilities to depression in early adolescence: Differential pathways to depressive symptoms by sex. *Journal of Adolescence, 37*(2), 165-174.
- Harkness, K.L., Alavi, N., Monroe, S.M., Slavich, G.M., Gotlib, I.H. & Bagby, R.M. (2013). Gender differences in life events prior to onset of major depressive disorder: The moderating effect of age. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology, 119*(4), 791-803.
- Johnson, D.P. & Whisman, M.A. (2013). Gender differences in rumination: A meta-analysis. *Personality and Individual Differences, 55*(4), 367-374.
- Keestra, A.L., Post, W.J. & Goorhuis-Brouwer, S.M. (2010). Behavioural problems in young children with language problems. *International Journal of Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology, 74*(6), 637-641.
- Luby, J. L. (2010). Preschool depression: The importance of identification of depression early in development. *Current Directions in Psychological Science, 19*(2), 91-95.
- Luby, J. L., Gaffrey, M. S., Tillman, R., Abril, L. M., & Belden, A. C. (2014). Trajectories of preschool disorders to full DSM depression at school age and early adolescence: Continuity of preschool depression. *The American Journal of Psychiatry, 171*(7), 768-776.
- Petersen, A. C., Sarigiani, P. A., & Kennedy, R. E. (1991). Adolescent depression: Why more girls? *Journal of Youth and Adolescence, 20*(2), 247-271.
- Rohde, P., Lewinsohn, P. M., Klein, D. N., Seeley, J. R., & Gau, M. (2014). Key characteristics of major depressive disorder occurring in childhood, adolescence, emerging adulthood, adulthood. *Clinical Psychological Science, 1*(1), 41-53.
- Sorensen, M. J., Nissen, J. B., Mors, O., & Thomsen, P. H. (2005). Age and gender differences in depressive symptomatology and comorbidity: An incident sample of psychiatrically admitted children. *Journal of Affective Disorders, 84*(1), 85-91.

Thapar, A., Collishaw, S., Pine, D.S. & Thapar, A.K. (2012). Depression in adolescence. *The Lancet*, 379(9820), 1056-1057.